

Electronic structure calculations of defect states in Ti-doped LiF

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates, using density functional theory (DFT), the localization of electrons and holes produced by irradiation in LiF crystals doped with Ti. We show that the Ti can act either as an electron trap, when located at an interstitial position of the LiF lattice, or as a trap for holes by substituting a Li atom. We also observe that an excess electron is localized in a Ti *p*-state while a hole localizes in a Ti *d*-state. The localization of the hole in this state when the Ti substitutes a Li is supported by results reported in the literature where it was assumed that the Ti substitute is a hole trap. The defect energy levels obtained in this work agree quite well with those reported in experiments.

1. Introduction

Lithium fluoride (LiF) is one of the typical alkali fluorides that has been extensively studied for many years. Mg and Ti-doped LiF are also the most common thermoluminescent (TL) dosimeters used in several applications. Previous studies of photo- and thermoluminescence of LiF reported that when LiF is doped only with Mg, the emitted light yield per radiation unit is relatively low (Zimmerman and Jones, 1967). However, the addition of a small amount of Ti increases the TL intensity by a factor of 10 or more, without changing the glow curve shape (Zimmerman and Jones, 1967).

Concerning the role of each dopant in the TL process, several experimental studies reported that glow peaks from Mg-doped LiF are the result of electrons thermally released from traps associated with the Mg impurity (Christy and Mayhugh 1972; Mayhugh et al., 1970; Mayhugh 1970). A recent density functional theory (DFT) study about the role of Mg on the LiF:Mg TL process, reported that both Mg impurity and F-centres are associated with electron traps (Massillon-JL et al., 2019). Regarding the Ti dopant, experimental work by Rossiter et al., (1971) concluded that Ti acts as an emission centre in LiF TL and is subject to the usual concentration quenching effect. Christy and Mayhugh suggested that the luminescent emission is associated with the trapping of a hole at the titanium site (Christy and Mayhugh 1972). Later, Davies performed electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) and electron nuclear

double resonance (ENDOR) measurements of Ti-doped LiF after radiation exposure. That study reported a centre of spin one-half identified as Ti³⁺ displaced by 0.2–0.3 Å in a <111> direction from a lithium site (Davies 1974). The possible structure of this center was suggested to be Ti³⁺F₃O₃²⁻, partially charge compensated. According to Townsend and co-workers, the Ti enters the LiF lattice substitutionally for Li⁺ in either the Ti³⁺ or Ti⁴⁺ state (Townsend et al., 1983), while these Ti complexes, modified by Mg in Mg-doped crystals, are responsible for the luminescence emission. More recently, Wu and co-workers (Wu et al., 2004) have theoretically investigated the local structure of the trigonal Ti³⁺ centre in the LiF crystal, reporting that the Ti³⁺ impurity is expected to substitute a host Li⁺ ion and shift away from its regular lattice site by about 0.19 Å. This was due to the strong electrostatic attraction of the O²⁻ triangle replacing the original F⁻ triangle (Wu et al., 2004).

In terms of optical absorption measurements, Jain and Sootha have studied the electrical and optical properties of Ti-doped LiF. They reported an optical absorption band at 207 nm (5.9896 eV) for the unirradiated LiF:Ti crystal, and two new bands at 240 nm (5.166 eV) and 270 nm (4.592 eV) for the irradiated LiF:Ti (Jain and Sootha, 1967).

The present work investigates the electronic structure of LiF:Ti using first-principles DFT calculations with the PBE0 hybrid functional. We analyse the localization of secondary electrons and holes upon irradiation, as well as the geometric displacements associated with the introduction of the Ti dopant and compare to experimental data.

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2. Materials and methods

The spin-polarized calculations were carried out with the CP2K open-source code (VandeVondele et al., 2005; Borstnik et al., 2014; Hutter et al., 2014, Lippert et al., 1997). We used the PBE0 hybrid functional that combines 25% Hartree–Fock (HF) exchange with 75% of the PBE semi-local exchange functional, while correlation is included via the PBE functional (Perdew et al., 1996; Adamo and Barone 1999). According to Mieke and Nink, Ti-doped LiF grown through the Czochralski method using several Ti compounds like TiO_2 , TiF_4 , K_2TiF_6 and metallic Ti, show the same glow curve shape and thermoluminescent response (Mieke and Nink 1979). This suggests that the only relevant dopant is the Ti. Therefore, in this work, we used a $4 \times 4 \times 4$ supercell of the pristine LiF (512 atoms) with a Ti atom as an interstitial, named LiF:Ti. Fig. 1 presents a perspective view of the LiF crystal structure with the Ti inserted at an interstitial position before relaxation. During the relaxation process, the Ti interstitial interacts with the surrounding lithium and fluorine atoms and exchange the charge when it is necessary to form Ti^{3+} or Ti^{4+} . The grey, green, and cyan symbols represent the F, Li and Ti atoms, respectively. To analyse excess electron and hole localization, we added a negative (unpaired electron) or a positive (hole) charge to the LiF:Ti system. Like in our previous work (Massillon-Jl et al., 2019), we used the double-zeta polarized DZVP-MOLOPT-SR-GTH basis set (VandeVondele J and Hutter 2007), optimized for norm-conserving Goedecker-Teter-Hutter pseudopotentials (Goedecker et al., 1996; Krack 2005). We used a plane wave cutoff of 1000 Ry for the density and a convergence threshold of 10^{-6} Hartree for the total energy self-consistency. The geometry was allowed to relax.

3. Results

A perspective view of the neutral LiF:Ti crystal structure in the x - y plane after geometry relaxation is shown in Fig. 2, where the displaced position of the Ti atom, along with the displacement of the closest Li atoms from their original positions, can be clearly observed.

Fig. 3a presents the structure of the LiF:Ti crystal in the presence of an excess electron. Note the similarity between Figs. 3a and 2,

Fig. 1. Perspective view of the LiF crystal structure in the x - y plane of the initial configuration with the Ti in an interstitial position within the LiF lattice. The grey, green, and cyan symbols represent the F, Li, and Ti atoms, respectively.

Fig. 2. Perspective view of the structure of the neutral LiF:Ti system in the x - y plane after geometry relaxation. The grey, green, and cyan symbols represent the F, Li, and Ti atoms, respectively. The red arrows indicate the new position of the displaced Li atoms while the orange lines the triangle formed by the three Li atoms.

Fig. 3a. Structure of the LiF:Ti crystal with an excess electron (perspective view in the x - y plane) after geometry relaxation ($\text{LiF:Ti} + e^-$). The grey, green, and cyan symbols represent the F, Li, and Ti atoms, respectively. The red arrows indicate the new position of the displaced Li atoms while the orange lines the triangle formed by the three Li atoms. Note the similarity with Fig. 2 indicating that the location of the Ti and the nearest Li atoms changes only slightly in the presence of an excess electron.

suggesting that in the presence of an excess electron, the location of the Ti and the nearest Li atoms changes only slightly. Fig. 3b shows the spin density isosurface (value $0.0031 e/\text{\AA}^3$) of $\text{LiF:Ti} + e^-$ —represented by the blue (positive) and red (negative) surfaces. As the LiF:Ti system does not have a net spin, the presence and the particular shape of the spin density in the Ti is an indication that an excess (unpaired) electron will tend to localize in a Ti $4p$ state.

Results for LiF:Ti with a hole are shown in Fig. 4a and b. Fig. 4a represents the geometric configuration. Interestingly, Fig. 4a indicates that, in the presence of a hole, the Ti atom becomes a Li substitute within

Fig. 3b. Spin density isosurface (value $0.0031 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^3$) from a perspective view of the LiF:Ti crystal in the x - y plane with an excess electron, after geometry relaxation ($\text{LiF:Ti} + e^-$). The grey, green, and cyan symbols represent the F, Li, and Ti atoms, respectively. The blue and red blobs represent negative and positive spin density isosurfaces, respectively.

Fig. 4a. Structure of the LiF:Ti crystal with a hole (perspective view in the x - y plane) after geometry relaxation ($\text{LiF:Ti} + h^+$). The grey, green, and cyan symbols represent the F, Li, and Ti atoms, respectively. The red arrows indicate the new position of the displaced Li atoms.

the LiF lattice, while the Li atom is displaced to become a Li interstitial. Fig. 4b displays the spin density isosurface (value $0.0042 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^3$) of $\text{LiF:Ti} + h^+$, represented by the blue (positive) and red (negative) surfaces. Similar to $\text{LiF:Ti} + e^-$, the presence and the shape of the spin density localized around the Ti is an indication that the electron has been removed from a Ti 3d orbital, leaving a hole there.

Fig. 5 displays the total projected density of states (PDOS) of the neutral LiF:Ti crystal, and also with an excess electron and with a hole. The purple lines display the contribution from the lithium orbitals, the green lines from the fluorine orbitals and the yellow lines from the titanium orbitals. The dashed lines represent the valence band maximum (VBM) and the conduction band minimum (CBM). The peaks situated between the VBM and CBM represent the defect states (DS). An energy gap of 12.075 eV has been reported previously for the pristine LiF with no localised DS within the gap (Massillon-JL et al., 2019) where the fluorine p -states were found to contribute to the VBM and the lithium s -states to the CBM. Note that the energy gap which is the difference between the CBM and the VBM may change with the presence of DS as can be seen in Fig. 5. In all three graphs, the presence of localised DS can be observed within the band gap region which will play the role of

Fig. 4b. Spin density isosurface of $\text{LiF:Ti} + h^+$ (value $0.0042 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^3$) after geometry relaxation. The grey, green, and cyan symbols represent the F, Li, and Ti atoms, respectively. The blue and red blobs represent negative and positive isosurfaces, respectively.

Fig. 5. Projected spin density of states as a function of energy for neutral and charged LiF:Ti calculated at the PBE0 level. The purple, green and yellow lines represent the contributions of Li, F and Ti atoms to the PDOS. The dashed lines represent the valence band maximum (VBM) and the conduction band minimum (CBM). The peaks situated between VBM and CBM represent the defect states (DS). The zero in the horizontal axis (0 eV) is placed at the location of the DS.

charge carrier trapping centres. These DS are originated either by the presence of the Ti dopants in the LiF material, due to the radiation itself, or both.

4. Discussion

Fig. 2 indicates that, after relaxation, the Ti atom in neutral LiF:Ti moves by 0.533 Å and stays at closest distances of 1.674 Å and 1.865 Å from a Li and a F atom, respectively. The presence of the Ti as an interstitial in the LiF lattice also induces the repulsive displacement of three Li atoms to create a planar triangle formed by three Li vacancies. The displacements of the three Li atoms are sizeable at 0.7973 Å, 0.756 Å and 0.812 Å. However, the Ti atom does not substitute any of the Li atoms displaced from their original position in the crystal lattice.

In the presence of an excess electron, the geometric configuration shown in Fig. 3a indicates that the Li atoms barely move from their original position in the neutral system (see Figs. 2 and 3a). The spin density for the LiF:Ti displayed in Fig. 3b clearly shows that the excess electron is localised in a $4p$ -state of the Ti atom. The geometry configuration depicted in Fig. 4a reveals that in the presence of a hole, the Ti dopant becomes a Li substitute, but is displaced by 0.13 Å approximately in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction from the Li site, whereas the displaced Li atom is moved towards a tetrahedral interstitial position of the LiF lattice. The spin density displayed in Fig. 4b indicates that the hole is localised in a $3d$ -state of the Ti, which was occupied in the neutral case. This means that, if Ti substitutionals are created in the presence of ionizing radiation, then they will be characterized as hole traps. According to Davies, the Ti is in the trivalent state following X-ray or γ -irradiation and lies at a substitutional cation site in the lattice displaced in a $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction (Davies 1974). However, the trivalent state was no longer observed after the crystals had been heated to 300 °C and yielded the thermoluminescence glow peaks used for radiation dosimetry (Davies 1974). The resulting position of the Ti within the LiF lattice in the presence of a hole and the associated spin density found in this work agree quite well with previously reported experimental and theoretical results where the Ti substitute has been associated with a luminescent centre (Christy and Mayhugh 1972; Wu et al., 2004; Townsend et al., 1983). A similar displacement of 0.2–0.3 Å of the Ti ion from the Li site was observed from EPR and ENDOR measurements (Davies 1974) but the center was not interpreted as a hole trap during irradiation. Since in the Davies's work, oxygen is included, future investigations that consider the inclusion of oxygen in the DFT simulation might shed light on the discrepancy observed between the nature of the Ti substitutional trap.

According to the PDOS reported in Fig. 5, both the neutral, LiF:Ti, and the charged system, LiF:Ti + e^- , exhibit up to three defect states (DS) while the charged system LiF:Ti+h⁺ shows only one. In this work, the energy levels of the defects are reported as the Kohn-Sham energy level of the CBM minus the energy of the DS, i.e., ($E_{\text{CBM}} - E_{\text{DS}}$). For the neutral LiF:Ti, all three DS are dominated by the Ti $3d$ -states hybridized with Li $2p$ -states. The energy levels of the neutral LiF:Ti are situated at 5.0162 eV, 0.994 eV and 0.710 eV, but only the 5.0162 eV is considered feasible and stable under typical conditions. Experimentally, an optical absorption band at 5.9896 eV with a half-width of 0.72 eV has been reported in the literature for the neutral LiF:Ti (Jain and Sootha, 1967) which agrees reasonably well with the value of 5.0162 eV obtained in this work. Note that the difference between our result and the experiment is about 0.97 eV. It is not clear whether this discrepancy with the experiment is due to the chosen functional which might not be quite accurate enough for the Ti as a transition metal or due to uncertainties in the experiment. To compare our previous results for the energy level of the DS in Mg-doped LiF (Massillon-JL et al., 2019), we found up to six different experimental works reporting the same value and the difference between the DFT calculations using the present (PBE0) functional and the experiment was only 0.22 eV. For the Ti-doped LiF, only one experimental measurement is available.

Concerning the charged system LiF:Ti + e^- , two DS are

predominantly associated with the Ti $3d$ -states and one with the Li $2p$ -states. The energy levels of these DS are 4.074 eV, 3.42 eV and 2.856 eV. In this case, all three DS are found to be feasible and stable under typical conditions. The DS observed on the PDOS (Fig. 5) for the charged system LiF:Ti+h⁺ is dominated by a Ti $3d$ -states and is situated at an energy level of 3.545 eV. In the presence of irradiation, two optical bands at 5.166 eV and 4.592 eV have been observed for LiF:Ti (Jain and Sootha, 1967). The energy difference between these two optical bands is about 0.574 eV. From the simulation, the difference between the energy level at 4.074 eV for the LiF:Ti + e^- and that at 3.545 eV for the LiF:Ti+h⁺ is about 0.529 eV, which is very close to the experimental value of 0.574 eV. These observations suggest that the Ti dopant assumes a dual role, acting as a trap for electrons when at a tetrahedral interstitial position, or as a trap for holes when substituting a Li atom.

5. Summary and conclusions

We have investigated the electronic structure of Ti-doped LiF after exposure to irradiation using simulations from first principles. The results indicate that the Ti dopant induces a sizeable distortion within the LiF crystal lattice by inducing the displacement of Li atoms away from their original positions. Upon irradiation, the Ti impurity stays at a tetrahedral interstitial position when negatively charged, i.e., capturing an excess electron. However, when the irradiation process leads to the creation of a hole by the removal of an electron from the Ti the Ti impurity becomes a Li substitute, albeit displaced by 0.13 Å from the Li site, in accordance with the 0.2–0.3 Å displacement reported by Davies (1974). This is at variance with the common wisdom that hole generation occurs via the removal of an electron from a F⁻ ion in the lattice, and subsequent neutralization of the F⁻ ion by transfer of an electron from the Ti impurity. The displaced Li ion becomes an interstitial. This dual character of the Ti impurity, behaving as an electron trap when interstitial, and a luminescence centre when substitutional, is consistent with experimental optical data and the calculated PDOS. Moreover, this picture, combined with the observation that the Mg impurities act essentially as electron trapping centres, can presumably explain the observed 10-fold increase in luminescence between LiF:Mg and LiF:(Mg, Ti).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Guelda Massillon-Jl: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Conrad S.N. Johnston:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Lorenzo Stella:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jorge Kohanoff:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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References

- Adamo, C., Barone, V., 1999. Toward reliable density functional methods without adjustable parameters: the PBE0 model. *J. Chem. Phys.* 110, 6158–6170.
- Borstnik, U., VandeVondele, J., Weber, V., Hutter, J., 2014. Sparse matrix multiplication: the distributed block-compressed sparse row library. *Parallel Comput.* 40, 47–58.
- Christy, R.W., Mayhugh, M.R., 1972. Thermoluminescence mechanism in dosimetry LiF. *J. Appl. Phys.* 43, 3216–3217.
- Davies, J.J., 1974. EPR and ENDOR of titanium-doped lithium fluoride. *J. Phys. C Solid State Phys.* 7, 599–609.
- Goedecker, S., Teter, M., Hutter, J., 1996. Separable dual-space Gaussian pseudopotentials. *Phys. Rev. B* 54, 1703.
- Hutter, J., Iannuzzi, M., Schiffmann, F., VandeVondele, J., 2014. CP2K: atomistic simulations of condensed matter systems. *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Comput. Mol. Sci.* 4 (15). CP2K version 6.1. www.cp2k.org.
- Jain, S.C., Sootha, G.D., 1967. Electrical and optical properties of Titanium-doped lithium fluoride crystals. *Phys. Status Solidi* 22, 505–516.
- Krack, M., 2005. Pseudopotentials for H to Kr optimized for gradient-corrected exchange-correlation functionals. *Theor. Chem. Acc.* 114, 145–152.
- Lippert, G., Hutter, J., Parrinello, M., 1997. A hybrid Gaussian and plane wave density functional scheme. *Mol. Phys.* 92, 477–488.
- Massillon-Jl, G., Johnston, C.S.N., Kohanoff, J., 2019. On the role of magnesium in a LiF:Mg, Ti thermoluminescent dosimeter. *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* 31, 025502.
- Mayhugh, M.R., Christy, R.W., Johnson, N.M., 1970. Thermoluminescence and color center correlations in dosimetry LiF. *J. Appl. Phys.* 41, 2968–2976.
- Mayhugh, M.R., 1970. Color centers and the thermoluminescence mechanism in LiF. *J. Appl. Phys.* 41, 4776–4782.
- Mieke, S., Nink, R., 1979. LiF:Ti as a material for thermoluminescence dosimetry. *J. Lumin.* 18/19, 411–414.
- Perdew, J.P., Ernzerhof, M., Burke, K., 1996. Rationale for mixing exact exchange with density functional approximations. *J. Chem. Phys.* 105, 9982–9985.
- Rossiter, M.J., Rees-Evans, D.B., Ellis, S.C., Griffiths, J.M., 1971. Titanium as a luminescence centre in thermoluminescent lithium fluoride. *J. Phys. D Appl. Phys.* 4, 1245–1251.
- Townsend, P.D., Ahmed, K., Chandler, P.J., McKeever, S.W.S., Whitlow, H.J., 1983. Measurements of the emission spectra of LiF during thermoluminescence. *Radiat. Eff.* 72, 245–257.
- VandeVondele, J., Hutter, J., 2007. Gaussian basis sets for accurate calculations on molecular systems in gas and condensed phases. *J. Chem. Phys.* 127, 114105.
- VandeVondele, J., Krack, M., Mohamed, F., Parrinello, M., Chassaing, T., Hutter, J., 2005. QUICKSTEP: fast and accurate density functional calculations using a mixed Gaussian and plane waves approach. *Comput. Phys. Commun.* 167, 103–128.
- Wu, S.-Y., Gao, X.-Y., Yan, W.-Z., Wei, W.-H., 2004. Theoretical studies of the local structure for the trigonal Ti^{3+} center in LiF crystal. *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A* 60, 2531–2535.
- Zimmerman, D.W., Jones, D.E., 1967. Photo- and thermoluminescence of LiF: (Mg, Ti). *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 10, 82–84.